

Formulation and evaluation of flurbiprofen colon targeted drug delivery system.

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Abstract

The intent of current investigation is to make colon targeting flurbiprofen matrix and compression coated tablets using time dependent hydroxypropyl methylcellulose, sodium alginate and pH sensitive Eudragit S100 that retard the liberation of drug in upper gastro intestinal system and also show progressive release in colon. The prepared formulations were optimized using dissolution tests and evaluated for colonic delivery. The optimized formulation of flurbiprofen showed 7.26 ± 0.05 (negligible release) in the initial lag period of 5 h followed by progressive release up to 99.27 ± 0.46 for 24 h respectively. The x-ray imaging study in human volunteers illustrated that the tablets arrived to colon with no loss of integrity in the upper gastrointestinal tract. C_{max} of colon targeted compression coated tablets was 10792.62 ng/ml at T_{max} 10 h for flurbiprofen where as in case of immediate release tablets the C_{max} was 15684.79 ng/ml at T_{max} 3 h for flurbiprofen which clearly indicates the capability of compression coated tablets to give colon targeting. Development of compression coated tablets was suitable to target flurbiprofen to colon.

Key words : Flurbiprofen, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose, sodium alginate, Eudragit S100.

Introduction

colon targeting in drug delivery is a technique designed to ensure that medications are released specifically in the colon, optimizing treatment for localized conditions such as ulcerative colitis, Crohn's disease, and colorectal cancer. This method also enhances the systemic absorption of drugs that are unstable or poorly absorbed in the upper gastrointestinal tract. Common techniques for colon targeting include pH-sensitive coatings that dissolve at the higher pH of the colon, time-dependent systems that release the drug after a specific period, and the use of prodrugs or carrier molecules activated by

colonic bacteria. Flurbiprofen, a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID), is used for its analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects in treating conditions like arthritis, dental pain, and postoperative pain. It inhibits cyclooxygenase (COX) enzymes, reducing the production of prostaglandins, which are mediators of inflammation and pain. However, oral administration of flurbiprofen can cause gastrointestinal side effects such as ulcers and bleeding. Colon-targeted delivery of flurbiprofen aims to reduce these adverse effects by bypassing the upper gastrointestinal tract and releasing the drug directly in the colon. This approach not only minimizes gastrointestinal toxicity but also improves the drug's bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy, offering a promising solution for safer and more effective NSAID therapy.

Materials

Flurbiprofen got gift sample from Alembic Mumbai, Spray dried lactose was received from Arabindo Hyd, Crosspovidone, Sodium lauryl sulphate, Talc, Magnesium stearate got from Merck Mumbai.

Methodology

Preformulation:

2.1.1.1. Determination of λ_{max} of FLB

The λ_{max} of FLB was determined using 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ standard solution in different pH buffers (0.1N HCl, 5.5 pH buffer and 7.4 pH buffers) by screening between 200-400 nm in UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Systronics 2202, Ahmedabad, India). The λ_{max} of FLB was found as 247 nm based on maximum absorbance, which is used in further studies.

2.1.1.2. Standard curve of FLB

Accurately weighed amount of FLB (100 mg) was shifted into a volumetric jar (100 ml), added 5 ml of methanol to liquefy FLB and the first stock (1 mg/ml) was prepared by adding 100 ml of methanol. 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solutions were prepared correspondingly. The absorbance was determined at 247 nm using a UV spectrophotometer and standard curve was plotted. Similarly FLB standard graphs in 5.5 pH and 7.4 pH phosphate buffers were plotted using the same procedure.

FLB solubility studies

The solubility studies were conducted in 0.1N HCl, 5.5 pH buffer,

7.4 pH buffer and water quantifying spectrophotometrically at 247 nm.

Powder characterization

The angle of repose (θ): measured by fixed funnel method using the given formula

$$\tan \theta = h/r$$

The powder blend bulk density (ρ_b) :

$$\rho_b = M / V_o$$

Tapped density (ρ_{tap}) (100 strokes/min):

$$\rho_{tap} = M / V_f$$

The carr's compressibility index: is computed from the bulk and using given formula

$$\text{Carr's Index} = [(\rho_{tap} - \rho_b) / \rho_{tap}] \times 100$$

Determination of weight variation

$$\% \text{ Deviation} = (\text{Individual weight} - \text{Average weight} / \text{Average weight}) \times 100$$

Determination of tablet thickness & Determination of tablet diameter

Random picking of twenty tablets were recorded thickness with the help of digital verniercaliper scale

Determination of tablet hardness

Monsanto hardness tester was used

Determination of friability

$$\% \text{ Friability} = [(W_1 - W_2) / W_1] \times 100$$

Determination of drug content

For estimation of assay, accurately weigh the 100 mg of powder from crushing the randomly selected ten tablets, and taken into a 100 ml measuring container. Prepare the solution with the help of phosphate buffer, made up to 100 ml, filtered and the samples (triplicate) were analyzed for FLB content.

Drug release study- In vitro

USP XXIV Type I dissolution apparatus (Electro lab, TDT-08L) was used to determine the FLB release profile from prepared tablets at 50 rpm speed, and at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ temperature. To facilitate and imitate the GI transit environment, tablets were subjected to different dissolution media. Initially, the drug release was carried out in 0.1 N HCl for 2 h, then 2 h in pH 5.5 buffer and followed in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 up to 24 h.

Kinetic studies :

To study the zero-order kinetics were studied by substituting the

data into given equation.

$$Q = K_o t$$

In case of first order kinetics, data substituted into below equation

$$\text{Log} (100 - Q) = K_1 t$$

To study Higuchi model kinetics, the data was substituted into the
beneath equation

$$Q = K_H t^{1/2}$$

Koresmeyer-peppas model explains the drug release mechanism from these formulations .

$$M_t / M_\alpha = Kt^n$$

RESULTS

Figure 1 Calibration curve in 0.1N hcl

Figure 2 Calibration curve in pH 5.5 buffer

Figure 3 Calibration curve in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer

Figure 4 solubility studies

Figure 5 Drug excipient compatibility studies DSC

Figure 6 drug excipient compatibility studies using FTIR

Table 1: Precompression parameters

Formulation	Angle of Repose*($^{\circ}$)	Bulk Density (g/cc)	Tapped Density (g/cc)	Carr's Index (%)
C1	27.87±1.56	0.324	0.382	15.03
C2	28.52±2.19	0.328	0.414	20.85
C3	31.36±0.79	0.336	0.388	13.23
C4	26.72±3.15	0.333	0.407	18.18
C5	30.22±0.57	0.330	0.412	19.71
C6	26.90±0.70	0.336	0.392	14.43
C7	29.23±2.74	0.324	0.382	15.32
C8	30.96±1.04	0.335	0.393	14.73
C9	28.84±3.37	0.337	0.382	11.70
C10	26.72±3.15	0.333	0.407	18.18
C11	26.72±3.15	0.333	0.407	18.18
C12	29.16±2.86	0.336	0.392	14.43
C13	28.76±2.18	0.324	0.382	15.32
C14	29.09±3.91	0.324	0.382	15.14

C15	29.02±2.68	0.327	0.394	16.99
C16	29.20±3.54	0.335	0.390	14.08
C17	29.20±3.54	0.335	0.390	14.08
C18	29.20±3.54	0.335	0.390	14.08

Table 2:post compression parameters

Formulation	Weight variation* (mg)	Hardness† (Kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Drug content‡ (%)
C1	374.15±3.20	6.50±0.20	0.22	98.60±2.03
C2	374.55±3.36	6.43±0.18	0.18	98.33±1.34
C3	374.10±3.08	6.23±0.31	0.13	98.20±1.72
C4	374.80±3.41	6.23±0.25	0.09	98.48±0.56
C5	374.30±2.49	6.37±0.15	0.22	97.21±0.16
C6	374.60±3.49	6.23±0.12	0.18	99.50±1.31
C7	374.20±3.04	6.27±0.32	0.22	99.16±0.33
C8	374.55±3.43	6.37±0.25	0.13	98.87±1.46
C9	374.95±3.30	6.27±0.12	0.09	99.30±2.00
C10	374.80±3.41	6.23±0.25	0.09	98.43±1.55
C11	374.80±3.41	6.23±0.25	0.09	98.20±1.21
C12	374.55±3.36	6.10±0.30	0.24	98.80±1.77
C13	374.45±3.35	6.30±0.17	0.12	97.00±0.44
C14	374.35±3.10	6.40±0.17	0.08	98.15±1.67
C15	374.85±3.12	6.37±0.15	0.16	97.97±0.50
C16	374.75±3.16	6.43±0.15	0.20	97.48±0.89
C17	374.75±3.16	6.43±0.15	0.20	100.25±2.07
C18	374.75±3.16	6.43±0.15	0.20	100.48±1.73

Table3: Dissolution data of FLB-HPMC K4M compression coated tablets

Time (h)	Cumulative percent of FLB released (Mean ± S.D.)				
	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
0	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00
2	12.38±0.62	2.60±0.18	2.25±0.14	2.06±0.26	1.89±0.07
4	93.39±8.98	4.27±0.18	4.08±0.19	3.92±0.28	3.59±0.04
5	-	9.15±0.10	8.89±0.35	8.24±0.36	7.81±0.19
8	-	42.69±1.19	34.08±0.73	28.64±0.92	22.99±0.40
12	-	45.84±1.11	41.40±0.46	43.51±1.04	27.44±0.38
18	-	52.89±1.47	52.55±0.59	56.67±1.87	34.17±0.58
24	-	99.64±1.76	79.99±3.11	73.68±2.14	48.21±0.94

Figure Dissolution profiles of FLB-HPMC K4M compression coated tablets

Table4: Dissolution data of FLB compression coated tablets with different viscosity grades of HPMC

Time (h)	Cumulative percent of FLB released (Mean ± S.D.)				
	C2	C6	C7	C8	C9
0	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00
2	2.60±0.18	32.00±1.03	26.79±0.48	1.93±0.13	1.18±0.09
4	4.27±0.18	98.37±1.37	80.37±3.40	3.68±0.23	2.57±0.08
5	9.15±0.10	-	104.14±0.29	8.29±0.33	9.17±0.25
8	42.69±1.19	-	-	31.97±0.86	18.32±0.57
12	45.84±1.11	-	-	44.63±1.32	26.88±0.84

18	52.89±1.47	-	-	57.44±1.79	32.88±0.29
24	99.64±1.76	-	-	75.02±2.61	39.44±1.06

Figure7: Release profiles from FLB compression coated tablets containing different viscosity grades of HPMC

Table5:.Dissolution data of FLB-SA compression coated tablets

Time (h)	Cumulative percent of FLB released (Mean ± S.D.)				
	C12	C13	C14	C15	C16
0	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00
2	11.96±0.33	8.67±0.24	5.24±0.14	1.82±0.31	1.30±0.10
4	73.39±1.10	23.04±0.69	15.95±0.20	3.52±0.23	2.74±0.05
5	103.43±0.29	58.05±1.78	40.66±1.04	7.22±0.31	4.45±0.06
8	-	70.64±1.65	49.80±0.93	53.14±0.69	31.75±0.77
12	-	80.11±2.22	69.44±2.00	66.00±1.82	51.02±0.96
18	-	95.36±1.63	86.94±2.31	81.70±1.54	68.04±1.13
24	-	-	103.82±1.96	99.68±1.73	81.49±0.68

Figure 8:Release patterns of FLB-SA compression coated tablets

Table 6:Dissolution data of FLB-SA-ED compression coated tablets

Time (h)	Cumulative percent of FLB released (Mean ± S.D.)		
	C16	C17	C18
0	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00
2	1.30±0.10	1.23±0.05	1.16±0.02
4	2.74±0.05	2.60±0.05	2.40±0.05
5	4.45±0.06	4.27±0.07	4.33±0.06
8	31.75±0.77	33.04±0.32	35.88±0.19
12	51.02±0.96	64.21±0.45	73.12±0.73
18	68.04±1.13	74.13±0.65	82.72±0.79
24	81.49±0.68	89.62±0.54	100.78±0.64

Figure9: Release patterns of FLB-SA-ED compression coated tablets

Table 7:Release kinetics of FLB compression coated tablets

Formulation	Zero order		First order		Higuchi	
	K_0 (mg/hr)	R ²	K_1 (hr ⁻¹)	R ²	K (mg/hr ^{1/2})	R ²
C1	-	-	-	-	-	-
C2	4.019	0.925	0.17733	0.792	19.91	0.813
C3	3.416	0.962	0.17273	0.797	17.06	0.859
C4	3.333	0.971	0.17503	0.808	16.70	0.872
C5	2.073	0.958	0.1543	0.787	10.52	0.885
C6	-	-	-	-	-	-
C7	-	-	-	-	-	-
C8	3.391	0.963	0.17733	0.797	17.05	0.872
C9	1.798	0.948	0.1566	0.755	9.246	0.897
C10	3.794	0.974	0.18885	0.814	18.84	0.860
C11	4.622	0.964	0.20266	0.801	23.01	0.855
C12	-	-	-	-	-	-
C13	5.519	0.852	0.20497	0.598	25.34	0.889

C14	4.462	0.942	0.1543	0.633	23.46	0.932
C15	4.676	0.942	0.19576	0.772	23.78	0.849
C16	3.872	0.952	0.19806	0.812	19.33	0.85
C17	4.31	0.931	0.20497	0.805	21.61	0.837
C18	4.857	0.927	0.21418	0.802	24.31	0.832

K_0 - Zero order rate constant, K_1 - First order rate constant, K - Higuchimodel rate constant and R^2 -Correlation coefficient.

Table 8: Release kinetics of FLB compression coated tablets

Formulation	K	n	R ²	MDT
C1	-	-	-	2.73
C2	2.3281	1.4983	0.951	13.71
C3	1.1363	1.4697	0.960	12.62
C4	1.2061	1.4776	0.965	11.71
C5	3.2434	1.3103	0.961	11.72
C6	-	-	-	2.35
C7	-	-	-	2.83
C8	1.0954	1.1591	0.950	11.59
C9	1.3280	1.3370	0.928	10.34
C10	1.4883	1.5747	0.947	12.16
C11	1.0534	1.6834	0.930	11.73
C12	-	-	-	3.20
C13	2.1677	1.5383	0.879	6.45
C14	1.868	1.4236	0.918	9.84
C15	1.4079	1.657	0.926	10.67
C16	1.7611	1.627	0.922	11.31
C17	1.8862	1.6862	0.911	11.00
C18	1.1964	2.9002	0.987	11.06

Conclusion:

Colon targeted tablets of FLB and KTM were prepared using HPMC and SA as time-dependent polymers and ED as pH sensitive polymer for colon targeting and they were characterized. From the results, it was concluded that the HPMC K4M was better polymer when compared to SA. When compared to matrix tablets compression coated tablets were superior to give colon-specific release of drug with less amount of drug release in upper GIT. In comparison of two drugs KTM requires high amount of polymer to give successful colonic release due to its high solubility when compared to insoluble FLB. The drug release from above formulations followed zero order profile and supercase II transport. DSC and FTIR spectral studies explained the absence of interactions between the drug and excipients and the accelerated stability studies showed stability of tablet. The *in vivo* x-ray imaging studies in human volunteers showed that the tablets arrived colon with no loss of tablet integrity upper GIT. The results of *in vivo* pharmacokinetic studies in humans proved that the colonic tablets were suitable not only to retard the drug release in upper GIT but also to deliver drugs to colon in slow manner in contrast to IR tablets. In conclusion, development of HPMC K4M-ED S100 compression coated tablets is a good approach to target the FLB in colon and time dependent HPMC K4M compression coated tablets is showed KTM release in colon.

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